

ANALYZING THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON PERFORMANCE OF TOURISM & HOSPITALITY FIRM'S: A STUDY OF NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION

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Abstract

This paper highlights the role of social media in the tourism industry. Social media provides various platforms to different stakeholders to communicate and exchange information among them. The essence of social media is growing rapidly in the tourism industry. More and more researchers are working on investigations in the areas of the impact of social media on many aspects of the tourism industry. The main objective of this research is to analyze the social media impact on hospitality firm's performance. Due to its dynamics and viral capability, tourism businesses need to formulate some guideline or framework before start using Social Media. This study includes two-way methodological approach; primary and secondary as well. Structured questionnaire was designed and filled from hospitality firms (Travel agencies/ tour operators) and secondary part is based on the existing literature.

Keywords: Social media, Hospitality Firm's, Performance, Facebook, Tourism

1. Introduction

Nowadays, social networking sites on the internet are handled more in daily life than the physical presence of individuals for interaction with each other. Twitter, Facebook, Linked-In, Whatsapp, Instagram, and YouTube are well-known among social media platforms. It is helpful to make the decision easier as well as assist the decision-making practice to choose the best offer for the travel regarding a particular destination. Numerous big and small firms of the tourism industry have adopted social media platforms to market their products or services. Internet-based services got mainstream in the tourism industry during the year 1995 in India. Tour and travel industry adopting the new method as social media to embrace the people and communicating with them as well as they should be prepared for the alterations in the behavior of customers and hopes on the horizon of tourism business. Destination marketing operators (DMO) recommended their standard customers for getting the best touring plan by giving the

customized packages to them. In view of wide challenges in this industry, as of now, various associations are making their sites by giving all data with respect to packages to draw in clients. These days even in India, travel services are offering on the web types of assistance by promoting remote destinations in a protected and efficient way. This is a direct result of more usage of smart phones among buyers. Present Indian homes are well furnished with web services and the use of internet services is expanding even in the rural regions. Yet, the tourism business is facing rivalry due to the presence of ICT (Wang et al., 2007). For all tourism promoting organizations, social media support is extremely fundamental with great substance so it will attract more clients. It is extraordinarily hard to make and put being utilized a fruitful travel site (Law et al., 2010). Regardless, for an effective social media accounts, the account should be suitably arranged, planned, and examine from time to time. It will be useful for the travel organizers. The travel services ought to use the high-level advancement in a superior way to pull in customers. The high-level automated development is going probably as a center individual between the travel businesses trained professionals and visitors.

Social Media

Social media is an event that changed the way of communication and interaction of people in the world. Adoption of social media are rapidly increased, during the last two decades and also now growing fastly and vastly in all fields such as educational, social, political, and tourism among the youth. It is being used more often than the physical involvement of individuals to interact. According to Richard and Guppy (2014) and Bhakuni and Aronkar (2012), the prevalence of social media sites has grown rapidly through a platform that leads some individuals online to a platform that is used by a big number of internet users. The most popular social networking platform is adopted by people as, Facebook, Twitter, My Space, Vibe, Pinterest, Instagram, Youtube, etc. Key reasons behind the growth of social media are the reach of smart phones and the internet to laymen. Kaplan & Michael, (2010) defines *Social Media* “A group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of User Generated Content” (Kaplan & Michael, 2010).

2. Literature Review

Social media in Travel

Holiday travel related purchases are considered complex due to the composite and experiential nature of the holiday travel product, involve high risks and as a result require extensive information search (Sirakaya & Woodside, 2005). Within such information search processes, consumers rely on other travellers' experiences as a mean to increase the exchange utility and decrease uncertainty (Kotler, Bowen, & Maken, 2010; Litvin, Goldsmith, & Pan, 2008; Yoo, Lee, & Gretzel, 2007). Just after the creation of the first virtual communities (Rheingold, 1993) it became apparent that their online content was perceived similar to recommendations provided by friends, family and “like-minded souls” (Fernback & Thompson, 1995; Wang, Yu, & Fesenmaier, 2002). Social media are therefore becoming increasingly important in travel planning, primarily for their function as vital information sources providing access to other

travellers' experiences (Chung & Buhalis, 2008). At the same time, apart from their function as information sources, social media enable storytelling, a usual post-travel activity, on a '24/7' basis to large audiences, and also provide a sense of belonging into virtual travel communities (Gretzel, Fesenmaier, & O'Leary, 2006). A number of studies focus on the impact and role of social media in travel related decisions: Gretzel, Yoo, & Purifoy (2007) found that online reviews posted in a travel related consumer review and rating website increase travellers' confidence during decision making, reduce risk, assist them in selecting accommodation and therefore facilitate decision making. P.Kumar & Nisha (2022) also found that social networking sites influenced the travel buying behavior of tourists. In their attempt to reveal the role of social media throughout the travel planning process, Cox, Burgess, Sellitto, & Buultjens (2009) found that social media are mostly used before the trip, while during and after the trip their use was very limited.

Social Media Marketing in Tourism and Hospitality:

The growth of the internet has allowed the hospitality industry to embark on various social networking sites (SNS) providing an effective competitive advantage. The use of internet marketing (IM) through social media platforms (SMPs) is an effective medium to drive the company's branding strategy. Social media marketing (SMM) facilitates induction of brand awareness (Mohammadian & Mohammadreza.,2012), enhance viral-spread of brand messages and brand democratization by inviting consumers to actively engage in the brand's meaning (Tuten,T.L.,2008), establish brand loyalty, enhance online brand reputation, drive sales and profits. Hoteliers should engage and effectively communicate with its target audience through SMM in order to stay ahead of competition within the hospitality industry. (Russell, J., 2010).

3. Objectives of the Study

A very few studies have been done in India for measuring the impact of social media in the tourism industry. Therefore, the main focus of the study will be to identify the impact of social media on the tourism industry, different practices of using social media adopted by the Indian tourism industry.

The followings are the main objectives of this study:

1. To find out preferred social media platforms adopted by the tourism industry
2. To study the contribution of social media in the tourism industry

Hypothesis 1: The choice of social media platforms is not significantly correlated with a company's performance.

4. Research Methodology

This study is conducted in Delhi-NCR with focusing on five major cities (Delhi, Gurugram, Noida, Faridabad and Ghaziabad). A structured questionnaire was designed on 5 point Likert scale for data collection from hospitality firms in the study area. A total of 125 firms were covered and out of them, 37 were tour operators, 59 were travel agencies and 29 were local carriers. Four guiding agencies were also included in this total sample size. The present study

was conducted using a probability sampling technique to collect the data. For descriptive analysis, firstly data was processed through version 20 of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

5. Data Analysis

Demographic profile of Firm's Staff

Table 1 shows the demographic profiles of all the respondents on the company side with the help of frequency and percentage analysis.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of respondents

Gender		Male			Female		
Frequency		75			50		
Percentage		60			40		
Age (in years)		25-40	41-55	56 and Above	Total		
Frequency		87	24	13	124		
Percentage		69.6	19.2	10.4	99.2		
Residence		Indian			Foreigner		
Frequency		125			00		
Percentage		100			00		
Education	Sr. Secondary	Graduation	Post. Graduation		Above	Total	
Frequency	38	49	26		12	125	
Percentage	30.4	39.2	20.8		9.6	100	
Professional Education of Owners/MD/CEO/Regional Head/National Head/Managers/Executives/supervisory lever staff		Certificate course	Diploma	Degree	Master Degree & Above	None	Total
Frequency		49	20	29	12	15	125
Percent		39.2	16.0	23.2	9.6	12.0	100.

Designation of respondent or Owners/ MD/ CEO/Regional Head/ National Head/ Managers/ Executives /supervisory lever staff		MD/CEO	Regional Head/ National Head	Sr. Manager /Manager	Sr. Executive /Executive	Others	Total
Frequency		6	12	47	35	25	125
Percent		4.8	9.6	37.6	28.0	20.0	100.0
Experience in Industry (in Years) of Owners/MD/CEO/Regional Head/ National Head/Managers/ Executives/ supervisory lever staff				0-5 Years	5-10 Years	More than 10 Years	Total
Frequency				55	31	39	125
Percent				44.0	24.8	31.2	100.0
Salary	Up to 2 Lacs	2-5 Lacs		5 Lacs or Above			
Frequency	64	48		13		125	
Percentage	51.2	38.4		10.4		100.0	
Status of Company	Multinational			National			
Frequency	30			95			
Percentage	24			76			

In this survey on the firms' end, out of total employees or staff, 60 percent are male while 40 percent are female, 69.6 percent are young which falls under the category of 25-40 years. 30.4percent of the respondents are Senior Secondary passed, 39.2 percent participants have a graduate degree. 39.2percent of the total respondents have a certificate course. In the context of designation inquiry of respondents this survey yield that out of the total participant of the survey 4.8 percent are MD/CEO, 9.6 percent have the post of Regional Head/National Head, 37.6 percent possess the post of Sr. Manager /Manager and 28.0 percent hold the designation of Sr. Executive /Executive while 20 percent belongs to another post. Regarding the question

of experience current survey revealed that 44 percent from the total respondent that has the experience of 0-5 years and 24.8 percent bears the 5-10 years' experience while 31.2 percent respondent falls under the category of more than 10 years' experience.

Companies Profile

The profile of companies/firms is presented in Table No. 2 as frequency and percentage analysis.

Table 2: Demographic Profile of Company's Firms

Location of the Company where it situated?	Delhi	Gurugram	Faridabad	Ghaziabad	Noida	Total
Frequency	51	25	13	12	24	125
Percent	40.8	20.0	10.4	9.6	19.2	100.0
Years of operation of Company?	1-5 Years	5-10 Years	More than 10 years			Total
Frequency	23	45	57			125
Percent	18.4	36.0	45.6			100.0
Do you use social media?				Yes	No	Total
Frequency				119	6	125
Percent				95.2	4.8	100.0
Do You Have Separate Social Media Advertising and Marketing cell?				Yes	No	Total
Frequency				99	26	125
Percent				79.2	20.8	100.0
Do you have any mobile application of social media for your Company?				Yes	No	Total
Frequency				88	37	125
Percent				70.4	29.6	100.0
No of years you are using social media for your Company?				0-5 Years	5-10 Years	Total
Frequency				63	37	125

Percent	50.4	29.6	100.0
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The above table (2) highlighted that in the context of the location of firms, it found after the analysis of data that out of the total firms only 40 percent firms belong to Delhi, 20 percent firms are situated in Gurugram, 10.0 firms from Faridabad are included while 9.6 percent and 19.2percent firms are located in Ghaziabad and Noida respectively.

79.2 percent of firms have a separate wing for social media and marketing on the other hand only 20.8 percent of firms devoid from it. 70 percent firms adopts social media-based mobile application for their firms while 29.6 percent are not used any kind of social media mobile application. 50.4 percent firms fall under the category of 1-5 years, 29.6.0 percent of firms came under the category of 5-10 years, while the category of more than 10 years has 20.0 percent firms.

Preferred social media platforms adopted by the tourism industry

There are many social networking platforms that exist in this modern world. Which social networking platforms are preferred by the tourism industry? In the current investigation, an attempt was made to know this through a survey with an organized questionnaire. The obtained results are shown as the table and descriptive mode as follows.

Most preferred Social Media platform for advertising and promotion.

Regarding the most preferred social media platform for advertising and promotion, it is found through this survey that Facebook is more preferred social media platform than WhatsApp is having 44.8 percent vote in responses of very frequently use while Twitter occupied very low preference as 20 percent of the total respondent under the category of very rarely prefer group.

Table 3: Most preferred Social Media platform

	Very rarely	Rarely	Average use	Frequently	Very Frequently	Mean	S.D.
Facebook	3.2	7.2	12.8	22.4	54.4	4.18	1.12
Twitter	20	15.2	11.2	29.6	24	3.22	1.47
LinkedIn	8	10.4	18.4	34.4	28.8	3.66	1.23
Instagram	7.2	8.8	20.8	43.2	20	3.60	1.12
WhatsApp	5.6	8.8	4.8	36	44.8	4.06	1.17
Pinterest	6.4	8	12.8	43.2	29.6	3.82	1.14
YouTube	8.8	12	16	35.2	28	3.62	1.26

Blog	14.4	11.2	17.6	44.8	12	3.29	1.24
TripAdvisor	9.6	12	30.4	33.6	14.4	3.31	1.15
Other (Please specify)	20.1	39.9	15.0	16.0	9.0	2.46	1.23

Most Social media Contents, Campaigns, Promotions, and Discounts.

As the reply of, do you run any social media Contents, Campaigns, Promotions, and Discounts? It came into light that 69.6 percent of respondents replied as yes while the answer of 30.4 percent of respondents is No (table 4.).

Table 4: Respondent responses regarding social media Contents, Campaigns, Promotions, and Discounts.

Do you run any social media Contents, Campaigns, Promotions, and Discounts?	Yes	No	Total	Mean	S. D.
Percent	69.6	30.4	100	1.3040	4.61

Most preferred Social Media platforms for your tourism firm or have the best responses from the customer.

In the context of the most preferred social media platform for tourism firms or customers, this survey presents that Facebook is very effective according to 36.8 percent of respondents while 9.6 percent of respondents reply as the trip advisor is very ineffective. As per the mean value of different social media plate forms, Facebook is the most preferred social media (3.74) firm followed by Blog (3.66) Instagram (3.60), Twitter (3.58) Pinterest (3.57), WhatsApp (3.55), YouTube (3.47) other 2.87. (Table 5)

Table 5: Most preferred Social Media platform by customer's responses

	Very rarely	Rarely	Average use	Frequently	Very Frequently	Mean	S.D.
Facebook	6.4	16.8	9.6	30.4	36.8	3.74	1.289
Twitter	5.6	10.4	24	40	20	3.58	1.09
LinkedIn	7.2	13.6	23.2	40	16	3.44	1.13
Instagram	8	11.2	16	41.6	23.2	3.60	1.19
WhatsApp	8.8	9.6	21.6	37.6	22.4	3.55	1.19
Pinterest	7.2	7.2	29.6	33.6	22.4	3.57	1.13

YouTube	9.6	12.8	22.4	31.2	24	3.47	1.25
Blog	8.8	9.6	10.4	48.8	22.4	3.66	1.18
TripAdvisor	9.6	10.4	21.6	38.4	20	3.49	1.20
Other (Please specify)	16.8	26.4	17.6	31.2	8.0	2.87	1.25

Social Networking Sites on the basis of overall use.

Regarding the rating of the Social Networking Sites on the basis of overall use, it is found after the analysis of a sample that Facebook is more preferred social media platform in overall use than Trip Advisor while very low preference social media platforms are YouTube represented and others which are represented by 10 percent and 20.0percent respectively.

Table 6: Rating of Social Networking Sites on the basis of overall use.

Variable	Very rarely	Rarely	Average use	Frequently	Very Frequently	mean	S.D.
Facebook	8	9.8	19.2	36.2	28.8	3.69	1.21
Twitter	9.2	12.4	20	33.6	24.8	3.62	1.18
LinkedIn	9.6	12.8	20.8	28.8	28	3.52	1.29
Instagram	8	8.8	17.8	37.4	28	3.68	1.20
WhatsApp	2.0	12	20.8	36.4	24.8	3.67	1.07
Pinterest	9.6	9.6	21.6	38.4	20.8	3.51	1.20
YouTube	10.4	7.2	23.2	33.6	25.6	3.56	1.24
Blog	8.8	16.8	10.4	32	32	3.61	1.32
TripAdvisor	7.2	9.8	22.4	37.2	22.4	3.60	1.14
Other (Please specify)	20.8	32.8	24.0	16	6.4	2.54	1.17

Facebook is the most preferred site in overall use it is demonstrated by this research however such kind of perception was in existence already but this research work confirms the pre-existing notion. On the other hand, this study also found that YouTube

and blogs rank at the fore in overall usage of respondents, whereas it seems and generally seems that people use blogs and YouTube in abundance.

Contribution of social media in tourism

In the modern phenomenon, social media has become very important for every business. The tourism industry is also not untouched by this, social media also has a big contribution to the tourism industry. During the present study, several dimensions of the use of social media were studied to find out the important contribution of social media in the tourism industry, for which information about social media and tourism was collected through a questionnaire from people who are associated with the tourism industry which is as follows.

Significance of social media on job performance.

Regarding the use of social media improves my job performance the result of the survey displays that out of valid responses 8percent of respondents are strongly disagreed, 9.6 percent of consumers disagree and 20percent of respondents are replied undecided while agreed and strongly agreed respondents are 39.2percent and 23.2percent respectively.

Table 7: Significance of social media on job performance.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean	SD
Using social media improves my job performance	8.0	9.6	20	39.2	23.2	3.56	1.18
Using social media tools enhances my effectiveness in my job	8	8.8	20.8	42.4	20.4	3.58	1.15
Using social media increase my job productivity	7.2	9.6	20.8	40	22.4	3.61	1.15
I find social media to be useful in my job	7.2	8.8	11.2	41.6	31.2	3.81	1.18
social media interactions do not require a lot of mental effort	9.6	8	4.8	44	33.6	3.85	1.25
My interface with social media is clear and understandable	8.4	8.8	9.6	44	29	3.78	1.20

In the perspective of using social media, tools enhance my effectiveness in my job the result of

gathered data indicates that 8percent of respondents are strongly disagreed, 8.8 percent of consumers are disagreed and 20.8percent of respondents are replied undecided while agreed and strongly agreed respondents are 42.4percent and 20.4percent respectively. In the context of using social media increase my job productivity, the result shows that out of vailed responses 7.2percent of respondents are strongly disagreed, 9.6 percent of consumers are disagreed and 20.8percent of respondents are replied undecided while 40percent are agreed and 22.4 percent of respondents are strongly agreed. Regarding social media interactions do not require a lot of mental effort the result of the research shows that from considered responses only 9.6percent of respondents are strongly disagreed, 8 percent of consumers are disagreed and 4.8percent of the respondent could not decide they respond as an undecided category apart from this a big number of the respondent about 44percent are agreed and 33.6percent of responded reply as strongly agreed.

Significance of social media on company’s performance

With regard to the question of how important aspects of social media affect the performance of the company, most of the respondents believe that social media has a significant impact on the performance of the company. As about the ease of doing work, 42.4 percent of the respondents believe that it is important and 30.4 percent people give it the category of very important, while in the question of time-saving, 36.8 percent of the respondents consider social media as important, and 32 percent respondent of survey considered extremely important. In the case of data management, the situation is more or less the same and 44.8 percent of the respondents consider it is important and 29.6 percent of people consider it is very important. At the same time, social media is important in terms of the best relationship between the customer and the company.

Table 9. Significance of social media on company’s performance

Question	Extremely unimportant	Unimportant	Neutral	Important	Extremely important	Mean	SD
Ease of operation	7.2	8.8	11.2	42.4	30.4	3.80	1.18
Time-saving	5.6	8	17.6	36.8	32	3.81	1.13
Data management	6.4	8	11.2	44.8	29.6	3.83	1.13
Customer relationship management	8.8	8	6.4	43.2	33.6	3.84	1.22

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Reduce operational cost	7.2	8	6.4	44.8	33.6	3.90	1.16
Quick responses	7.2	8.8	7.2	44	32.8	3.89	1.17
Attracting new customers	7.2	8.8	10.4	42.4	31.2	3.82	1.19
Retaining existing customers	7.2	11.2	10.4	40	31	3.76	1.21
Enhance customers' satisfaction	9.6	7.2	8	42.4	32.8	3.84	1.19
Improve sales growth	8.8	5.6	8.8	36.8	40	3.96	1.18
Increase Profitability	5.6	7.2	9.6	44	33.6	3.93	1.10
Increase market share	8.8	8.8	11.2	42.4	28.8	3.76	1.19
Instant feedback	7.2	8.8	10.4	45.6	28	3.78	1.16

Maximum 43.2 percent of the respondents consider it is important while 33.6 percent consider it is very important. Only 8.8 percent are considered very important and 8 percent are considered important. Respondents also rated social media as important in reducing operating costs, of which 44.8 percent give the category of very important and 33.6 percent important. Social media is able to provide instant feedback on company actions about 44 percent important and 32.8 percent of respondents consider it very important whereas only 7.2 percent of the people believed that social media is very unimportant in relation to quick responses, while 8.8 percent of the respondents considered it important. With regard to the question of attracting

new customers, a maximum of 42.4 percent are considered, it was very important and 31.2 percent respondents have given their opinion in favor of important, and on the other hand, 11.8 and 7.2 respondents were in favor of the category of unimportant and very important respectively. Regarding the question retaining existing customers, the opinion of the respondents is not different, maximum of 40.1 percent of the respondents are giving importance to social media, while 31.1 percent are in favor of the category of very important. In relation to the increase in sales growth, 40 percent of the respondents consider social media to be very important and 36.8 percent as important. Even in terms of increase probability, a maximum of 44 percent participant of survey considers social media is important and 33.6 percent very important. Even on the question of increasing market share, most of the respondents are in favor of social media, and 42.4 is important and 28.8 is very important. On the question of instant feedback, 45.6 percent of respondents consider it important and 28 percent very important. Whereas only 7.2 are considered very important and 8.8 percent are considered important, while 10.4 percent of the respondents are in the neutral category (table 9).

To measure the hypothesis '**The choice of social media platform is not significantly correlated with company's performance**', we calculate the Pearson correlation coefficient in SPSS-20. The Pearson correlation is used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship that exists between the choice of social media platforms and the company's performance. The results of the Pearson correlation are displayed in the table below.

The Pearson's correlation (r) is shown a positive correlation between Facebook and Time saving (0.05), Reduce operational cost (0.063), improve sales growth (0.03), increase market share (0.02). But the magnitude or strength of correlation or association is very low, as all values are near to zero. But the correlation is not statistically significant as all signs. 2 tail values are above 0.05. Rest values show a negative correlation with low strength of negative association. All negative correlation is also not statistically significant except 'retaining existing customers' (sign. 2 tailed 0.04) which showed significant association.

Table 10: Result of hypothesis

Variables	Facebook		Twitter		LinkedIn		Instagram		WhatsApp		Pinterest		YouTube		Blog		TripAdvisor		Others	
	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-	Pearson	Sig. (2-
Ease of operation	-.01	.027	-.01	.027	.241**	.001	-.008	.035	.013	.017	-.001	.002	-.003	.003	.002	.001	.017	.005	.001	.027
Time saving	.005	.061	-.41**	.000	.37**	.000	-.016	.008	.32**	.000	.004	.005	-.009	.032	.008*	.004	.33**	.000	-.008	.037
Data management	-.011	.021	.001	.092	.006	.005	-.012	.017	-.018*	.004	-.011	.023	.004	.005	.006	.006	-.001	.027	.005	.053
Customer relationship management	-.007	.045	-.27**	.000	.20*	.003	-.001	.025	.015	.009	-.005	.009	-.005	.009	.003	.002	.27**	.000	.000	.002
Reduce operational cost	.0063	.048	.015	.011	-.009	.003	.000	.096	-.011	.022	-.001	.008	.002	.005	-.003	.005	-.26**	.000	.002	.084
Quick responses	.0056	.054	.18*	.005	-.002	.007	.000	.099	-.019*	.003	.000	.003	.001	.008	.003	.007	-.26**	.000	.009	.003
Attracting new	-.011	.021	.001	.092	.006	.005	-.012	.017	-.018*	.004	-.001	.023	.004	.005	.006	.006	-.001	.027	.006	.053

custo mers										1 1										
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Enha nce custo mers , satisf actio n	- 0. 0 4	0 .6 5	- .2 0 *	0 .0 3	.3 1* *	0	- 0. 09	0. 3 5	.2 4 **	0 .0 1	0 .0 7	0 .4 4	- 0 .0 6	0 .4 8	0 .1 7	0. 0 7	0. 0 7	0 .0 6	0 .5 4	
Impr ove sales grow th	0. 0 3	0 .7 1	- .1 8 *	0 .0 4	- 0. 03	0 .7 1	- .1 8 *	0. 0 5	0. 1	0 .2 6	- 0 .1 8	0 .3 9	- 0 .0 7	0 .4 6	- 0 .1 3	0 .1 6	.2 5 **	0. 0 1	- 0 .0 8	0 .4 1
Incre ase Profi tabili ty	- 0. 1	0 .2 6	0	0 .9 7	- 0. 04	0 .7	- 0. 05	0. 5 5	- .3 7 **	0	- 0 .0 1	0 .9 6	0 .0 3	0 .7 2	0 .1 1	0 .2 1	- 0. 07	0. 4 2	0 .0 7	0 .4 6
Incre ase mar ket shar e	0. 0 2	0 .7 9	0. 1 5	0 .1	- 0. 15	0 .0 9	0. 0 2	0. 7 9	.2 3 *	0 .0 1	- 0 .0 5	0 .5 9	0	0 .9 7	0 .0 4	0 .6 6	0. 1 5	0. 1	- 0 .0 7	0 .4 4
Insta nt feed back	- 0. 1	0 .2 7	- .4 0 *	0	.3 1* *	0	- .2 0 6 *	0. 0 2 1	0. 1 2	0 .1 7	- 0 .0 2	0 .8	- 0 .0 8	0 .3 9	- 0 .1 2	0	.2 9 **	0. 0 1	- 0 .0 1	0 .8 7

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

For Twitter and performance, r value is positive for Data Management (0.01), reduced operational cost (0.15), quick responses (0.18), attract new customers (0.01), retaining existing customers (0.10), increase profitability (0.00), increase market share (0.015). All of these variables also show a low positive correlation ($r < .3$). Rest of the variables moderate to low negative correlation. Six of the elements show a significant association between twitter and

time saving (0.00), customer relationship management (0.00), quick responses (0.05), enhanced customers satisfaction (0.03), improved sales growth (0.04), and instant feedback (0.00) (table 4.13)..

For correlation between LinkedIn and the company's performance, three variables were moderately correlated and also statistically significant as all sign. 2 tail values are less than 0.05 (Time-saving (0.37;0.00), enhanced customers' satisfaction (0.31;0.00), instant feedback (0.31;0.00). Four of the variables showed a low positive correlation and six showed a low negative correlation. Out of these only two variables (ease of operation; 0.01, customers relationship management; 0.03) were statistically significant in correlation.

For the correlation between Instagram and the company's performance, only one variable (Increase market share; 0.02) showed a positive correlation. Reduced operation cost and quick responses showed zero correlation and the rest ten variables were negatively correlated. In testing significantly with sign two-tail, only two were significantly correlated (Improved sales growth; 0.05 and instant feedback 0.021).

Similarly, WhatsApp was moderately correlated with time-saving (0.32) and increase profitability (0.37). These two are also significantly correlated as per the sign two-tail value. Six variables (ease of operation, customer relationship management, enhanced customers satisfaction, improve sales growth, increase market share, and instant feedback). Five of the variables were negatively correlated. Out of these 11 variables, six variables (data management, quick responses, attracting new customers, retaining existing customers, enhance customer satisfaction, increase market share) were significantly correlated as sing. Two tail value was less than 0.05.

Pinterest showed a low positive correlation with only one variable i.e time saving (0.04). The rest of the 12 variables showed a negative correlation. And none of these variables showed a significant correlation. Similarly, YouTube was positively correlated with five variables, and the rest 8 variables were negatively correlated. None of the variables showed a significant correlation as a sign. Two tail value was more than 0.05. A similar trend was showed with Blog, 7 variables showed low positive correlation, and 6 were negatively correlated. Only two elements (time-saving; 0.04, retaining existing customers; 0.04) showed significant correlation based on the sign. Two tail values. In correlation with TripAdvisor, only one element showed moderate correlation i.e time saving (0.33), it is also statistically significant with 0.00 sign. Two tail values. Five variables are positively correlated and seven are negatively correlated. Out of these seven variable showed significant correlation i.e Ease of operation (0.05), Customer relationship management (0.00), reduce operational cost (0.00), quick responses (0.00), retaining existing customer (0.04), improve sales growth (0.01), instant feedback (0.001). In terms of other social media platforms, 9 variables are positively correlated and 4 are negatively correlated. None of the variables showed a significant correlation assign the two-tail value was more than 0.05.

Conclusion

It was observed in this study that the adoption of social media plays a very vital role in the

tourism industry. These days Facebook is the most preferred social media platform in the tourism industry. Social media increase job performances, very helpful to achieve the organizations' goal and very significant for company performance as well as increase and decrease the profit of firms. Social media reviews and comments also played a very important role in the brand image and profitability of the company. Social media has proved to be very helpful in saving both time and money for tourists. Offers received through media attract tourist's more than traditional advertising. Therefore, this study showed that not everyone can expect that social media results are always positive; sometimes it can lead to misconceptions, criticism, and opinions, so there is still need to be considered different aspects of social media. Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, blogs, and websites are the social networking sites that individuals often use. Social media applications served as an opportunity for faster dissemination of information, especially for low-cost tourism establishments. The travel industry businesses may constantly utilize online media as their promotional tools however they ought to be prepared for the guaranteed activity to the issues that may emerge. Future examinations may likewise be directed utilizing different factors to additionally affirm the consequence of this investigation.

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